

**Taxonomic Note on *Xylotrechus* (s. str.) *ibex* (Gebler, 1825)
(Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Cerambycinae)**

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Abstract: The status of *Xylotrechus rectangulus* (Motschulsky, 1875) is downgraded to subspecies rank and the name is accepted as *Xylotrechus ibex rectangulus* (Motschulsky, 1875), **stat. nov.**

Acronyms of the collections:

ES - collection of E.V. Sergeeva (Tobolsk, Russia).

KH - collection of K. Hadulla (Troisdorf, Germany).

MD - collection of M.L. Danilevsky (Moscow, Russia).

ML - collection of Maxim Lazarev (Moscow, Russia).

MS - collection of M.E. Smirnov (Ivanovo, Russia).

MSPU - collection of Moscow State Pedagogical University
(Moscow, Russia).

VU - collection of V.E. Ustinov (Moscow, Russia).

ZMM - collection of Zoological Museum of Moscow University
(Moscow, Russia).

Results

Xylotrechus ibex (Gebler, 1825) in the traditional sense occupies a huge area from Western Europe to Pacific Ocean, including Mongolia, Korea and China (Aurivillius, 1912; Plavilstshikov, 1940; Löbl & Smetana, 2010; Danilevsky, 2020). It is very common in certain areas of Siberia, but rather rare in Europe.

Recently the taxon was divided in two species (Hass et al., 2024):

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X. ibex (Gebler, 1825) (= *angulosus* Motschulsky, 1875: 150 - described from “environs du Lac Inderskoe près de l'Oural”) - distributed in Europe and Western Asia (105 specimens studied) and *X. rectangulus* (Motschulsky, 1875) (= *fugitivus* Thieme, 1881 - described from “Amur”, = *interruptus* Pic, 1902e - described from “Sibérie, ?Japon”) - distributed in the most part of Siberia, Mongolia, Korea and China (12 specimens studied) on the bases of many small characters, which are discussed below. Both taxa are nowhere sympatric.

Hass et al. (2024) wrongly included Japan in the area of their *X. rectangulus* (Motschulsky, 1875), which is absent in Japan. Only rare cases of import of specimens from the mainland are known.

According to the lectotype designations (Hass et al., 2024), *X. ibex* was described from “Altai”; *X. rectangulus* - was described from “Daourie méridionale“ - on the bases of holotype label.

14 morphological distinguishing characters were listed by Hass et al. (2024: 162), including 6 based on genitals, which cannot be discussed here, as significance of observed small differences is doubtful and the limits of individual variability were not shown by the authors. Recently many publications show a great level of variability in Cerambycidae genitals inside one species, or inside one population (see: Hodek, 2021: 1168 for *Agapanthia* Audinet-Serville, 1835; Lazarev, 2022: 221-222 for *Echinocerus* Mulsant, 1862; 2023: 68, 71, 76, 79 for *Pilemia* Fairmaire, 1864).

According to Hass et al. (2024), *X. ibex* is characterized by several attributes: dense yellow-brown pubescence of elytral pale stripes, sutural elytral stripe distinct back to transverse subapical elytral stripe, subapical elytral stripe wide, middle elytral stripe is fused with sutural stripe, male elytra between middle and subapical stripes often with distinct pale pubescence (Fig. 6), subapical stripe complete, prosternal process narrow, mesosternal process narrow.

From the other side in *X. rectangulus* (sensu Hass et al., 2024): elytral pale stripes are yellowish and not so dense, sutural elytral stripe absent, subapical elytral stripe wide, middle elytral stripe is separated from sutural stripe, elytra between middle and subapical stripes without pale pubescence, subapical stripe partly reduced laterally, prosternal process wide, mesosternal process wide.

In fact, all distinguishing characters are not quite stable. Many of them can be observed in a small number of specimens only. Most

of described features are mixed in many known populations. So, both taxa must be accepted as subspecies of one species: *X. ibex ibex* (Gebler, 1825), **stat. nov.** (Figs 1-6) and *X. i. rectangulus* (Motschulsky, 1875), **stat. nov.** (Figs 7-9).

The density and color of elytral pale stripes are rather individual for each specimen from eastern and western populations, and in general both are not real distinguishing characters.

Sutural elytral stripe is really more or less developed in *X. i. ibex* and is absent in *X. i. rectangulus*, but sometimes it is considerably reduced in *X. i. ibex*.

Subapical elytral stripe can also be rather wide in the nominative subspecies as in the neotype of *Clytus angulosus* Motschulsky, 1875 (Abb. 2a - Hass et al., 2024: 155) from Uralsk (now in Kazakhstan).

Middle elytral stripe is always separated from sutural stripe in *X. i. rectangulus* (Figs 7-9), but can be also separated in *X. ibex ibex*, as for example in the lectotype (Abb. 1a - Hass et al., 2024: 155), in the neotype of *Clytus angulosus* (Abb. 2a - Hass et al., 2024: 155), in a female from Altai (Fig. 1), or in a female from Samara Region (Fig. 3).

Pale elytral pubescence between middle and subapical stripes in males (Fig. 6) is a very rare character and is known in a small number of *X. i. ibex* specimens. It is absent in specimens from Volga river valley (Figs 2-3), from Tyumen Region (Figs 4-5), from Germany (Abb. 3b - Hass et al., 2024: 156), as well as in the neotype of *Clytus angulosus* Motschulsky, 1875 (Abb. 2a - Hass et al., 2024: 155) from Uralsk (now in Kazakhstan).

Subapical stripe is often very narrow in *X. i. ibex*, as for example in its lectotype (Abb. 2a - Hass et al., 2024: 155) or just contrary, rather wide in *X. i. rectangulus* (Fig. 9).

Prosternal process in all available specimens of *X. i. rectangulus* is extremely narrow.

Moreover both taxa were never observed to be sympatric, which clearly indicates their subspecies nature.

Material. *X. ibex ibex*: 1 female, Russia, Altai Republic, Artybash, 15.6.1981, N. Krivosheina leg. - MD; 1 male, E Kazakhstan, 20 km N Zyryanovsk (now Altai), Putintsevo, 8-29.6.2006, K. Hadulla leg. - MD; 1 male with same

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label - KH; 1 male, Russia, Samara Region, Zhiguli, 6.7.1952, V. Grechkin leg. - ZMM; 1 female from same locality, 13-15.7.1952, V. Grechkin leg. - ZMM; 1 male, 1 female, Russia, Tyumen Region, Aromashevo District, 7 km NNW Slobodchiki, "Alabuga" reserve, 2-4.7.2024, E. Sergeeva leg. - ES.

X. ibex rectangulus

1 female, Russia, Tuva Republic, Ishtii-Khem, 7.1974, M. Danilevsky leg. - MD; 2 males, 2 females, Russia, Amur Region, Kundur, 28.5.1975, M. Danilevsky leg. - MD, ML; 1 male, Russia, Khabarovsk Region, Bychikha, 16.5.1976, A. Kompantsev leg. - ML; 2 males, Russia, Maritime prov., Arseniev env., 7.1990, R. Čermak leg. - MD; 1 male, 6 females, Russia, Maritime prov., 30 km NW Arseniev, 44°23'10"N, 133°4'35"E, 300 m, 27.6.2018, A. Shamaev leg. - MD; 1 male, Russia, Maritime prov., Lazo env., 18.7.2006, M. & L. Smirnov leg. - MD; 1 female, Russia, Maritime prov., Lazo reserve, 43°15'17"N, 134°07'59"E, 17.7.2005, K. Makarov leg. - ML; 1 male, 1 female, Russia, Maritime prov., Sokoltchi, 27-28.6.1979, A. Kompantsev leg. - MD, ML; 1 female, Russia, Maritime prov., Muraveika, 27.7.1988, S. Nikireev leg. - MD; 1 female, Russia, Maritime prov., Kedrovaya Pad', 9.5.1967, B. Mamaev leg. - MD; 1 male, Russia, Maritime prov., 20 km SE Ussuriysk, Gorno-Tayozhnoe, 23-25.6.2021, V. Ustinov - VU; 1 female, Russia, Maritime prov., Samarka, 15.6.1990, S. Khvylya - VU.

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Figs 1-6. *Xylotrechus ibex ibex*: 1 - female, topotype, Russia, Altai Republic, Artybash, 15.6.1981, N. Krivosheina leg., photo by M.L. Danilevsky; 2-3 - male (2) and female (3), Russia, Samara Region,

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Zhiguli, 6.7.1952, V. Grechkin leg., photo by M.L. Danilevsky; 4-5 - male (4) and female (5), Russia, Tyumen Region, Aromashevo District, 7 km NNW Slobodchiki, "Alabuga" reserve, 2-4.7.2024, E. Sergeeva leg., photo by E.V. Sergeeva; 6 - male, Kazakhstan, East-Kazakhstan Region, Putintsevo, 8-29.6.2006, K. Hadulla leg., photo by M.L. Danilevsky.
Figs 7-9. *Xylotrechus ibex rectangulus*: 7-8 - male (7) and female (8), Russia, Maritime prov., Lazo District, Preobrazhenie, 14.7.2004, M. & L. Smirnov leg. (MS), photo by M.E. Smirnov; 9 - female, Russia, Maritime prov., 50 km SW Ussuriysk, 480 m, 29.V.2019, A. Zaitsev leg. (MSPU), photo by K.V. Makarov.

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